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NEW ENGLAND JOURNAL OF MEDICINE - A BIBLIOMETRIC STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The study presents the Bibliometric analysis of articles published in the New England journal of Medicine. There are a total of 2740 articles published during the years 2006-2010. The study attempts to highlight the distribution of articles, affiliation wise distribution of articles, year wise authorship pattern, year wise Impact factor of articles, year wise distribution of length of articles, country wise distribution of articles, subject wise distribution of articles, year wise distribution of references of articles, contribution according to thrust areas.

KEYWORDS: *New England Journal of Medicine, Scopus, Bibliometrics, Citation analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

Bibliometrics is one of the research methods which are useful in the field of Library and Information Science. The word bibliometrics is a combination of two words 'biblio' and 'metrics' which are derived from the Latin and Greek words, it means the application of mathematics to the study of bibliography. Products like Social Science Citation Index, the Science Citation Index or the Arts and Humanities Citation Index (Web of Knowledge) are very helpful for

conducting bibliometrics research. The database Scopus of Science Direct is equally productive for bibliometric studies. Bibliometric research uses various methods of citation analysis to establish relation between authors and their work. When one author cites another author then a relationship is established that is called citation analysis.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The authors have chosen New England Journal of Medicine from <http://www.freemedicaljournals.com/>. In this site Journals are arranged according to Free Medical Journal (FMJ) impact, ISI Impact factor and Scimago Journal Rank (SJR). Out of these Medical Journals New England Journal of Medicine has a maximum Free Medical Journal (FMJ) impact i.e. 46,604, ISI Impact factor i.e. 47,050 and Scimago Journal Rank (SJR) i.e. 3.412. The Embargo period of this Journal is six months. Scopus covered this Journal from 1947 to till date. The periodicity of this Journal is weekly. It has completed 365 volumes and volume 366 numbers 10 is going on. The study covers volume 354 to 363 i.e. from 2006-2010. This study limited to 2740 articles. In this present study, the Scopus citation database has been used. Scopus is one of the comprehensive abstract and citation databases of peer-reviewed literature and quality web sources. As per Scopus citation database, there are 2740 articles published in the New England Journal of Medicine from 2006 to 2010. The collected data have been analyzed and is presented in the form of tables and figures

DATA COLLECTION AND INTERPRETATION

- 1. YEAR WISE DISTRIBUTION OF ARTICLES:** Table 1 show that there are volumes 354 to 361 from the year 2006-2010. In year 2009 there are two volumes i.e. 360 and 361 has maximum 570 (20.80 %) and in the year 2006 number of articles are 527 (19.23%) are minimum . Out of total no. of articles are 2740 articles 556 articles published in 2007, 546 articles published in 2008 and 541 articles published in the year 2010.

TABLE1. YEAR WISE DISTRIBUTION OF ARTICLES

Year	Volume No.	Articles	Total Articles	%age
2006	354	256	527	19.23
	355	271		
2007	356	273	556	20.29
	357	283		
2008	358	274	546	19.93
	359	272		
2009	360	284	570	20.80

	361	286		
2010	362	266	541	19.74
	363	275		
Total			2740	

2. AFFILIATION WISE DISTRIBUTION OF ARTICLES: In table 2 top five affiliations have been selected. Total numbers of articles are 2740 out of which Harvard Medical School has maximum 273 (9.96%) contribution and University of California, San Francisco has minimum 91(3.32%) contributing.

TABLE 2. AFFILIATION WISE DISTRIBUTION OF ARTICLES

Year/Affiliation	Harvard Medical School	Massachusetts General Hospital	Brigham&Women's Hospital	VA Medical Centre	University of California, San Francisco
2006	56	61	28	23	12
2007	47	54	28	22	23
2008	58	52	40	22	17
2009	55	49	36	22	13
2010	57	50	32	20	26
Total	273	266	164	109	91
%age	9.96	9.71	5.99	3.98	3.32

3. YEAR WISE AUTHORSHIP PATTERN OF ARTICLES: Table 3 & figure 2 indicates that maximum authorship pattern consists of two authors and more than 8 authors & more. Out of total 2740 articles 1014 (37%) articles are contributed by two authors and 864 (31.53%) articles are contributed by 8+ authors. Minimum 73 (2.66%) are contributed by 6 authors. There are 328 (11.98%) articles which are contributed by Single author.

TABLE 3. YEAR WISE AUTHORSHIP PATTERN OF ARTICLES

Authorship Pattern	Year					Total
	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	
Single	74	76	67	60	51	328
2 authors	188	205	194	220	207	1014
3 authors	28	25	25	33	27	138
4 authors	19	29	24	25	29	126
5 authors	22	28	29	19	24	122
6 authors	15	17	15	12	14	73
7 authors	22	15	11	16	11	75
8 authors & more	159	161	181	185	178	864

FIGURE 2 YEAR WISE AUTHORSHIP PATTERN OF ARTICLES

4. YEAR WISE CITATIONS OF ARTICLES: Table 4 shows number of citations maximum fall in 1-20 slabs (818) and minimum citations fall into category 81-100 (79). There are 764 articles which have Zero citations. As the trend shows that Zero citations are increasing since the year 2006 to 2010. In category 21-40 and 41-60 citations numbers of articles are increasing like 18-29-29-34-63 and 19-21-28-36-53 respectively.

TABLE 4. YEAR WISE CITATIONS OF ARTICLES

No. of citations	Year					Total
	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	
Zero	106	129	137	183	209	764
1-20	172	174	166	157	149	818
21-40	18	29	29	34	63	173
41-60	19	21	28	36	53	157
61-80	19	31	23	26	16	115
81-100	11	21	16	14	17	79
101-200	62	72	70	64	26	294
201-300	33	27	37	26	05	128
301-400	28	21	19	13	03	84
Above 400	58	31	21	17	00	127

FIGURE 3 YEAR WISE CITATIONS OF ARTICLES

5. YEAR WISE DISTRIBUTION OF LENGTH OF ARTICLES: Table 5 indicates that the length of the most of articles falls in the category of 1-4 and 9-12 pages. Maximum numbers of articles that are 1026 (37.45%) with 9-12 pages. category and 648 (23.65%) have pages between 1 to 4 and Articles with 13+ pages are 169 (6.17%) which is minimum.

TABLE 5. YEAR WISE DISTRIBUTION OF LENGTH OF ARTICLES

1 Pages	Year wise distribution of Articles						Total	%age
	Year							
	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010			
1-4	130	136	126	136	120	648	23.65	
5-8	76	78	69	78	65	366	13.35	
9-12	190	204	198	215	219	1026	37.45	
13 & More	36	32	46	28	27	169	6.17	
Total	527	556	546	570	541	---	----	

FIGURE 4 YEAR WISE DISTRIBUTION OF LENGTH OF ARTICLES

6. COUNTRY WISE DISTRIBUTION OF ARTICLES (TOP 10): Table 6 & Figure 5 shows that maximum articles are published by authors belonging to the United States are 1326(48.39%) between 2006-2010. For this study top ten countries are taken out which Switzerland has minimum 79 (2.88%) articles in the total. United Kingdom has 276 (10.07%), Canada has 212 (7.74%) contribution.

TABLE 6. COUNTRY WISE DISTRIBUTION OF ARTICLES (TOP 10)

Sr.No.	Name of the country	Year						
		2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	Total	%age
1.	United States	259	289	280	212	286	1326	48.39
2.	United Kingdom	35	63	79	45	54	276	10.07
3.	Canada	25	51	45	43	48	212	7.74
4.	Germany	39	36	48	41	37	201	7.33
5.	France	26	31	48	34	29	168	6.13
6.	Netherlands	19	25	29	32	36	141	5.14

7.	Italy	22	25	30	26	25	128	4.67
8.	Australia	21	22	29	17	24	113	4.12
9.	Belgium	13	15	21	14	18	81	2.96
10.	Switzerland	19	13	17	10	20	79	2.88

FIGURE 5 COUNTRY WISE DISTRIBUTION OF ARTICLES

7.YEAR WISE DISTRIBUTION OF REFERENCES GIVEN BY ARTICLES -Table 7 indicates that total references used by articles. Maximum average reference per article is 17.80 in 2007. In the year 2006 minimum average reference per article is 16.92. In the year 2008 references per article is 17.11, 2009 references per article are 17.60 and 2010 references per article is 17.15 which are very close.

TABLE 7. YEAR WISE DISTRIBUTION OF REFERENCES OF ARTICLES

Year	Total articles	Total references	Average reference per article
2006	541	9154	16.92
2007	570	10150	17.80
2008	546	9344	17.11
2009	556	9789	17.60
2010	527	9036	17.15

FIGURE 6 YEAR WISE DISTRIBUTION OF REFERENCES OF ARTICLES

8. CONTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO THRUST AREAS (Top 10): In this table contribution according to thrust area are 2740 for articles, 1703 for male and 1660 for females. For this study top ten thrust areas are selected out these 876 are from the trust area of controlled studies and 2687 from human thrust area, 2213 for priority journal.

TABLE 8. CONTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO THRUST AREAS (TOP 10)

Sr.No	Thrust Areas	Year					
		2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	Total
1.	Article	527	556	546	570	541	2740
2.	Human	518	547	534	559	529	2687
3.	Priority Journals	430	452	441	457	433	2213
4.	Humans	415	439	427	455	430	2166
5.	Male	340	343	334	336	350	1703
6.	Female	319	338	347	342	314	1660
7.	Adult	310	319	325	338	319	1611
8.	Case Report	244	280	286	297	276	1383
9.	Middle Aged	186	202	197	206	185	976
10.	Controlled Study	188	181	169	175	163	876

FIGURE 7 CONTRIBUTION ACCORDING TO THRUST AREAS (TOP 10)

CONCLUSION

The New England Journal of medicine is reputed journal in the field of Medicine. It has passed a long journey starting from 1812 till today (200 years). All the old issues of New England journal of Medicine (NEJM) can be accessed from its archive portal (<http://www.nejm.org/medical-index>). One very significant feature of the NEJM is its multimedia content. Readers can hear or download multimedia version of articles as well as interviews of reputed scientists. A bibliometric analysis of total 2740 articles from the year 2006 to 2010 shows that in year 2009 vol 361 issues are 27 and percentage of the number of articles is more in vol 355 in 2006.

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